

THE ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF NATIONAL AND UNIVERSAL VALUES IN THE SPIRITUAL DEVELOPMENT OF YOUNG PEOPLE

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Abstract: This article analyzes the history, migration processes, and stages of development of Uzbek diasporas that have formed in countries worldwide, particularly in Europe. It examines the activities of the Uzbek diaspora in Germany, Great Britain, France, Turkey, and other European nations, highlighting their role in preserving national and cultural values, promoting their native language, and strengthening social, economic, and cultural ties with Uzbekistan. Furthermore, the article provides a scholarly assessment of the significance of diaspora organizations in societal life and their contemporary development trends.

Keywords: Uzbek diaspora, European countries, migration, ethnic communities, Germany, Great Britain, France, Turkey, national identity, cultural heritage, diaspora organizations, international cooperation, compatriots, integration processes.

Where there is peace, there is progress and confidence in the future. This can be clearly understood once again from the words of our First President Islam Karimov: "There is no development without peace, and without development, there is no future." One of the important conditions for peace is tolerance and interethnic harmony.

In the process of globalization occurring in the world, issues related to national diversity, national minorities, and diasporas in the socio-spiritual life of the world's countries are placed on the agenda as topical issues. Currently, the widespread nature of migration processes on a global scale also raises problems related to national minority groups in various countries. These problems are manifested to one degree or another in various regions of the world and are the cause of certain confessional, ethnic, racial, territorial, and other types of contradictions, conflicts, and clashes. In this regard, the Office of the UN High Commissioner for National Minorities (OHCHR) focuses its international activities on identifying and preventing the aforementioned conflicts and solving problems.

Hundreds of higher educational institutions and scientific centers around the world are conducting scientific research on issues of interethnic relations, ethnic conflicts, and their consequences. Thus, through the analysis of concepts and terms, the systematization of the theoretical and methodological foundations for studying national policy in the Soviet state, the socio-philosophical aspects of interethnic relations, the true essence of the national policy of the Soviet state, the causes and tragic consequences of the Soviet state's policy of deregulation against peoples and nations, and the factors that influenced the formation of Meskhetian Turks as a nation are being researched from a scientific and theoretical perspective.

During the years of independence, great attention has been paid in Uzbekistan to the issues of improving interethnic relations, forming and developing a culture of tolerance and humanism, creating equal opportunities for all citizens regardless of their nationality and religion, and further developing the work of educating the younger generation in the spirit of respect for national and universal values.

Since time immemorial, our people have lived in friendship and brotherhood with representatives of various nationalities. Our kind and generous people provided shelter in their homes to representatives of many nationalities who were evacuated to our country during the Second World War and were repressed during the Soviet era, and stood by them during their difficult times. The neighborhood of people of such nationalities as Koreans, Germans, Turks, Rolyak, and Crimean Tatars, who share these Uzbek qualities, has settled permanently in this country and lives in our Motherland with the friendly relations characteristic of our people. They value Uzbekistan as their native land.

As the head of our state, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, noted at a meeting with activists of national cultural centers at the "Uzbekistan" Palace of International Forums on January 24, 2017, "from the first days of independence, our great leader attached special importance to strengthening interethnic harmony as an important factor in ensuring peace and prosperity." In his historic speech on the declaration of independence, he noted: "All opportunities will be used to protect the constitutional rights of representatives of all nationalities living in our republic, to create all conditions for the development of their culture, national traditions, and for speaking and studying their native language."

The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, along with defining the legal and legal foundations for the independent development of our society, has created broad opportunities for the effective development of the principles of democratic justice and freedom in the social and spiritual life of our country. Our Basic Law clearly reflects the equal enjoyment of democratic rights and freedoms and the possibility of achieving material well-being for all citizens of various nationalities living in our independent country.

The head of our state pays special attention to ensuring interethnic harmony and states in his speeches: "As you all know, interethnic and interreligious tension is currently intensifying in various regions of the world, and nationalism and religious intolerance are gaining momentum." These problems are destroying the state and dividing society, serving as a base for radical groups and movements. In such a complex situation, strengthening friendship and harmony among people of different nationalities and religions in our country is becoming increasingly important for us. There is no doubt that this serves as a reliable guarantee of peace and tranquility in our country, as well as a basis for increasing the creative potential of our people and their confidence in the future.

The Constitution of independent Uzbekistan is a reliable legal guarantee of a new society. During its preparation and adoption, it was strictly taken into account that the state sovereignty of Uzbekistan must be based on the equality of citizens regardless of race, nationality, religion, language, place of birth, social origin, or political beliefs.

Since the first years of independence, special attention has been paid in Uzbekistan to the issues of improving interethnic relations, developing a culture of tolerance and humanism, creating equal opportunities for all citizens regardless of their nationality and religion, and raising the younger generation in the spirit of respect for universal human values. Specifically, the Republican International Cultural Center (1992), the Republican Center for National Idea and Ideology (1996), the Republican Center for Spirituality Promotion (1998), the Coordinating Council for the Development of National Cultures under the Ministry of Culture and Sports (1997), and the Committee on Interethnic Relations and Friendly Relations with Foreign Countries (2017) were established under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

This has increased the relevance of tasks such as preserving and developing the history, culture, spiritual values, national traditions, and customs of all nations and ethnic diasporas living in Uzbekistan, treating them with respect, preserving and developing their customs, and harmonizing interethnic relations. The adoption of the Action Strategy for five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 defines the tasks of strengthening interethnic and interfaith peace and harmony in such important areas as ensuring security, interethnic harmony, and religious tolerance, which also requires raising the ongoing work to a new level.

Today, more than 130 nations and nationalities live in peace and tranquility on the territory of our Motherland. One of these nations is the Turkish diaspora. The history of this nation's entry into the territories of our homeland dates back to the distant past.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the issue of interethnic relations and harmony is considered one of the most pressing issues. For as long as the peoples living in our country live in peace and harmony, peace in our country will be eternal.

The large-scale reforms carried out in the Republic of Uzbekistan during the years of independence served as the foundation for strengthening national statehood and sovereignty, ensuring security and law and order, the inviolability of state borders, the rule of law in society, human rights and freedoms, an atmosphere of interethnic harmony and religious tolerance, and created the necessary conditions for a decent life for our people and the substantiation of the creative potential of our citizens.

At a meeting dedicated to the 25th anniversary of the Republican International Cultural Center, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, noted: "During the years of independence, a new stage has begun in the development of interethnic relations in our country." The development of a culture of tolerance and humanism, the strengthening of interethnic and civil harmony and accord, and the upbringing of the younger generation on this basis in the spirit of love and devotion to the Motherland have been defined as one of the most important priorities of state policy in Uzbekistan.

In our republic, conditions have been created for the legal, theoretical, and practical foundations of the policy of interethnic harmony and religious tolerance. As early as 1992, the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, I.A. Karimov, formulated an important principle: "Ensuring civil peace and interethnic harmony is the key to the constitutional order," which serves as the theoretical basis for all reforms.

In the first years of our independence, the role of the state program in solving the national issue, stabilizing and improving interethnic relations was expressed in the following way: "This historical experience teaches us that no noble intentions can justify the actions of politicians and individuals who strive for big politics, who try to create well-being for their people and maintain this state based on the discrimination and restriction of other peoples. Nevertheless, such attacks currently exist and are very noticeable. "It is necessary to remember them and remain vigilant."

In general, spiritual factors and culture have always served as an important condition for resolving the issue of interethnic relations in a civilized manner. At the same time, spirituality and enlightenment are factors of social stability, the nation is the unity of spirituality, spirituality is the foundation of the state, and the state is the support of spirituality.

One of our most important achievements is the fact that representatives of more than 130 nations and nationalities live in peace and harmony in our country today. Given the invaluable role of the 137 national cultural centers operating in our country, strengthening interethnic friendship and harmony will continue to be one of the priority areas of our national policy. We must not forget that achieving the social unity of representatives of various nationalities and ethnic groups living in Uzbekistan as a single people, uniting them around our national ideology, strengthening our country's independence, and achieving sustainable development and progress is one of the most important tasks. Therefore, ensuring interethnic harmony, solidarity, stability, and, of course, cooperation in our country has become one of the priority tasks of state policy.

Used literature:

- 1.I.A.Karimov "Erishgan marralar bilan chegaralanmasdan, boshlagan islohotlarimizni yangi bosqichga ko'tarish – bugungi kundagi eng dolzarb vazifamizdir". 23-tom. T., - "O'zbekiston". 2015.
- 2.M.S.Gafarli, A.CH.Kasayev. "Rivojlanishning o'zbek modeli: tinchlik va barqarorlik – taraqqiyot asosi" T., "O'zbekiston"-2001.
- 3.Мусаев О. "Миллатлараро муносабатларнинг шаклланиши" // Жамият ва бошқарув. 2009.
- 4.K.Xonazarov. "Mustaqillik va yoshlarni baynalmilal ruhda tarbiyalash" T., - 1998.